

Data management cooperation in practice: Lessons learned

Workshop

*LIBER RDM Working Group
6 July, 2022
LIBER Conference, Odense, Denmark*

Workshop introduction

The workshop will cover experiences and lessons learned from library involvement in research data management co-operations and projects of the last five years.

Current roles and future implication will be discussed.

Agenda:

9:00 Welcoming words

Introduction to RDM WG – Mari Elisa Kuusniemi

- EOOSC-Nordic cooperation on CTS certification work - Mari Elisa Kuusniemi, Liisi Lembinen
- Miriam Braskova and Francesco Varrato recorded presentation
- Skills4EOOSC - skills for engaging in the EOOSC - Richard Dennis, Royal Danish Library
- Q and A

10.15-10.30 – Coffee break

10.30 - 11.55 Discussion: skills to participate/run projects in different levels (institutional, national and international).

11:55 Closing words

LIBER RDM Working Group

The Research Data Management Working Group (RDM WG) was established out of two motivations.

- 1) to help libraries secure a critical role in the 21st century scholarly information infrastructure and,
- 2) to recognize research data as valuable academic resources that need to be managed, shared and preserved to foster research and science.

The following library professionals from the LIBER network participate in this working group.

The Research Data Management Working Group is part of the Research Infrastructure section of our 2018-2022 Strategy.

For questions about the group's work, please see the [Research Data Management Working Group page](#) or contact the group chair [Mari Elisa Kuusniemi](#).

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Resources

Research libraries can have a key role in Research Data Management (RDM), consisting of supporting the entire data life cycle through knowledge, skills, infrastructure and tools.

<https://libereurope.eu/working-group/research-data-management/documents-resources/>

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Share knowledge.

Find out more:

<https://libereurope.eu/working-group/research-data-management/R>
[Research Data Management Working Group - LIBER Europe](#)

Everyone working in a LIBER library is welcome!

THANKS!

Enjoy the workshop

